

The Importance of English in the Development of International Relations and Diplomacy

Linguistics

Keywords: English language, diplomacy, international relations, international institutions.

Fatos Gjata

“Aleksandër Xhuvani” University. Faculty of Human Sciences. Elbasan, Albania.

Abstract

This paper analyses the way English became an official language of international relations and diplomacy. Among the diplomatic languages, English is the most widely used and it is the first choice of masses and elites. Its election as a language of diplomacy and international relations was not accidental, but it was based precisely on the economic and political status of the states that used it and the role they had in the international extent. A diplomatic language is of special importance as it does not appear as a simple means of communication but it is the main pillar of diplomatic content, and it has been like that since the early beginning of the diplomatic function. This language, which has been used during the meetings and works of international institutions has already reached the characteristics of a global language. English continues to preserve its intact leader's status that enables positive conclusions of diplomatic agreements between numerous and diverse allies.

1. Introduction

The use of English is a phenomenon that has spread in Europe, but also to the rest of the world. This has happened despite the development of Britain and the United States of America in industry, economy, culture, etc. Before the 20th century, French was considered as a basic language, so it was also studied as the first language in many high schools of that time. Despite this, English was not completely hidden. It was studied as a second language since the beginning of the 20th century, a period in which it became a world language¹.

English is considered as the official language of international relations, focusing in particular on its role in the development of diplomacy. The greatest development of English occurred in the post-war years.

THE LIST OF COUNTRIES ACCORDING TO ENGLISH SPEAKING PEOPLE		
COUNTRIES	% of English speakers	Total of English speakers
USA	94.2	298,444,149
India	10.35	125,226,449
Pakistan	49	92,316,049
Nigeria	53	82,941,000
United Kingdom	97.74	63,962,000
Filipine	56.63	57,292,884
Germany	64	51,584,000
Bangladesh	18	29,398,158
Canada	85.63	28,360,240

¹ James B. Russell, *German Higher Schools: The History, Organization and Methods of Secondary Education in Germany* (1899), 270.

Egypt	35	28,101,325
France	39	25,500,000
Italy	34	20,300,000
Ghana	66.67	18,000,000
Australia	97.03	17,357,833
Thailand	27.16	17,121,187
South Africa	31	16,424,417

Tab. List of countries according to English speaking people.

Fig. English speaking ability in different countries of the world.

Fig. Countries where English is an official language

Graph. Using English in Different Areas (%)

2. English Language and International Relations

The representatives of international bodies needed to talk to each other, share opinions during their meetings. Communicating could be easier if each of them would speak in his own language. That thing was initially enabled by the presence of specialized translators. Despite the fact that this procedure enabled the preservation of equal dignity for all, the greater the number of languages became, the more difficult the translation of speeches and international agreements was. This made the translation process quite expensive and impractical. For this reason the use of translators became almost impossible. It was necessary to use one single language to avoid such situations

After the end of World War I, a significant part of the United Nations member states officially recognized English as an official language. The prevalence of English as a lingua franca is also indicated by the fact that more than half of the UN member countries prefer communication in English. Something like that has happened with other international bodies. Almost all the most important commercial and political leaders prefer to conduct international communications in English².

The European Union is the most important European organization that makes cooperation between member states easier or aims at being its part. It was necessary to establish English as an official language of this organization in order to make possible a more efficient cooperation. United Nations works are carried out precisely in this language, including all kinds of international meetings between heads of states, summits, etc.

International Laws, decrees, talks, or debates are all carried out in English. NATO is also a world-wide organization that works in English because the need for its member states' cooperation has led to the use of this single language.

The League of Nations is another important global organization. From its beginnings in 1919, importance was given to the language that would be used to enable the development of its meetings. It was initially a European body where the English, French and Spanish languages were used.

An English language feature is the use of idioms to further enrich the expressions used in the arena of international relations or policies. In international politics, the term "lame duck" has often been used to define a political representative who has lost his originality and authority.

One of the abbreviations used is NIMBY, which means "Not In My Back Yard" not in my yard. This abbreviation is used in those cases when the representatives of a certain country convey the concern of their citizens about the development of a new or highly dangerous technology.

² Barbara Crossette, "At the UN French Slips and English Stands Tall," June 16, 2002.

Another widely used abbreviation is BANANA - Building Absolutely Nothing Anyone Near Anything. This abbreviation used in international politics implies a policy banning the construction of something that may bother those who already reside in a particular area. This term is widely used in the field of environmental safety to show disagreement with some environmentally harmful behaviors.

‘More than 100 countries have a great need for a language uniformity’³. ‘The presence of many people in international organizations can lead to confusion and disorder with regard to the use of a particular language’⁴. Something like this also reveals the difficulties of communication as a result of the presence of a large number of spoken languages in different countries. Despite this, English is the most widely used language in international relations and policies. There are altogether more than 12,000 international organizations that have declared English as their official language.

3. English language and diplomacy

*Language is not a simple tool, but it is often the core of the diplomatic profession*⁵.

Diplomacy is the core of relations between different states or organizations. There are some definitions concerning its meaning. *We can consider diplomacy as the application of intelligence and tact, in the development of official relations between governments of independent states*⁶.

English got mainly developed in the field of diplomacy when the Treaty of Versailles was written in English, as well as in French, the language used by diplomacy at that time. Diplomatic meetings attach great importance to the oral communication of the participants. It is therefore necessary to analyse the oral communication requirements. Oral communication remains one of the clearest communications, it is the core of personal contact and there are less chances of misunderstanding. Written communication via telegrams, emails, etc., are very useful, but it can never take the place of a friendly or confidential communication conducted with the presence of two or more parties⁷.

Diplomats are appointed by their state to enable foreign policy representation and implementation. Due to the importance of duty, diplomats must possess multidimensional knowledge. The language used by diplomats is English, which has already had the characteristics of a global language. Diplomatic language is of special importance as it does not appear as a simple tool but it is the main pillar of the diplomatic call and it has been like that at the early beginning of the diplomatic function.

³ McArthur, *Gjuhët Angleze*, Cambridge University Press, 1998.

⁴ De Mauro, T., *Fjalor Italian*, Paravia, 2000.

⁵ Stanko Nick.

⁶ Ernest Mason Satow, “A Guide to Diplomatic Practice”.

⁷ Georges Gougenheim. *Les mots français dans l’histoire et dans la vie*. Paris, 1996.

4. Conclusions

The prevalence of English as a lingua franca is indicated by the fact that more than half of the UN member countries prefer communication in English. This is also the case with other international bodies.

The European Union is the most important European organization that facilitates easier cooperation between member states or aims at being its part. English has reached international use for global relations. The use of idioms in English enables further enrichment of expressions used in the arena of international relations or policies.

Diplomacy is the core of relations between different states or organizations. The language used by diplomats is English. Diplomatic language is of special importance as it does not appear as a simple tool but it is the main pillar of the diplomatic call and it has been like that since the early beginning of the diplomatic function.

English got mainly developed in the field of diplomacy when the Treaty of Versailles was written in English. The laws, decrees, talks or international debates are all done in English.

The need for the cooperation of its member states has led to the use of a single language, which is precisely the English language.

5. References

- Agrawal, A., Horton, J., Lacetera, N., & Lyons, E. (2013). *Digitization and the contract labor market: A research agenda* (No. 19525). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Altbach, P, G. Teichler, U. 2001. 'Internationalization and exchanges in a globalized university'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*
- Avgerou, C. (2010). Discourses on ICT and development. *Information Technologies & International Development*, 6(3), p.1.
- Barbara Crossette, (June 16, 2002), "At the UN French Slips and English Stands Tall".
- De Mauro, T., (2000), *Fjalor Italian*, Paravia.
- Ernest Mason Satoë, "A Guide to Diplomatic Practice".
- Georges Gougenheim, (2000), *Les mots français dans l'histoire et dans la vie*. Paris.
- James B. Russell. *German Higher Schools: The History, Organization and Methods of Secondary Education in Germany* (1899). P. 270.
- McArthur (1998). *Gjuhët Angleze*. Cambridge University Press.